

Technocrats Supervising EU Agencies? Political Attitudes of Management Board Members¹

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the underexplored vertical relationship between European Union agencies (EUAs) and the member states. It is argued that member states' representation on the EUAs' management boards (MBs) may be considered an instance of vertical political accountability and legitimacy—a feature that EUAs are conventionally seen to be lacking. Additionally, this paper analyzes the political attitudes/preferences of the national representatives on EUA MBs because these preferences might also influence the factual behavior and hence the domestic accountability of these board members. However, the empirical data based on an original online survey reveal a rather ambivalent picture concerning vertical political accountability. Strong direct political accountability relationships seem not to be in place, and existing vertical accountability relationships show a technocratic/professional rather than a democratic orientation. This finding is also supported by empirical evidence that MB members possess technocratic rather than democratic attitudes towards accountability.

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1. Introduction

After the establishment of the first two European Union agencies (EUAs) in the mid-1970s, many have followed, especially since the second half of the 1990s. Now, in 2013, there are 35² EUAs at work with headquarters all over Europe (excluding EURATOM and Executive Agencies). This massive proliferation of EUAs, in number as well as in scope and tasks, is attracting increasing academic attention. A particular focus is the question of their legitimacy and accountability. This question is mostly assessed with regard to the horizontal relations between EUAs and other European Union (EU) institutions (e.g. the Council, European Parliament, Commission, Court of Justice). In contrast, this paper concentrates on the underexplored vertical relationship between EUAs and their national counterparts and the member states in general. In particular, member states' representation on the management boards (MBs) of EUAs may be considered an instance of vertical accountability. By focusing on these MBs, the paper investigates the extent to which the national representatives on these boards are accountable to their particular member states (e.g. to government and parliament). This may be seen as an indicator of the vertical political accountability of the EUAs as a whole. Additionally, the paper offers an empirical assessment of the political attitudes and role perceptions of these national representatives, which may also influence their behavior and actions on the MB and hence also their accountability.

The aim of this contribution is conceptually and empirically descriptive. It draws on original data from an online survey of national representatives on eight EUA MBs. The aim is to gain insights into the accountability and the attitudes of EUA MB members on two substantive attitudinal dimensions: perceptions relating to legitimate and accountable EUAs and EU governance in general, and perceptions about the preferred level of centralization of political authority in the EU. By doing this, the study takes an approach similar to that adopted in the studies by Hooghe (2001) on Commission officials and Wonka and Rittberger (2011) on EUA staff and is based on similar survey questions, thus allowing comparisons to be made.

The following chapter gives a short summary of the agency phenomenon in the EU and summarizes existing accounts of EUAs' legitimacy and accountability. The third part then deals with the vertical relationship between EUAs and the member states and proposes

² See http://europa.eu/agencies/regulatory_agencies_bodies/index_en.htm

criteria for how these vertical relationships should be organized to serve as a channel of political accountability for EUAs. In the fourth part, a short description of the methods of data collection is given, followed by the results of the empirical assessment of the vertical accountability relationships and the attitudes of EUA MB members. Finally, the results are analyzed, and the potential of the existing vertical relationships is evaluated.

2. Delegation of power to EU agencies

The nature and relevance of delegation in the EU is increasingly being explored by scholars with an interest in European integration. More and more regulatory tasks are being assigned to EUAs, which are often set up in sensitive policy fields dealing with societal risks (e.g. chemicals, food safety, and medicines) and, in some areas, they are replacing the traditional committee system as the EU's main regulatory institution (Gehring and Krapohl 2007; Krapohl 2004). Some authors are already talking about an "epidemic agency fever" (Christensen and Laegreid 2007, 15), a "Europe of Agents" (Pollack 2003, 392), and "agencification" (Cassese 2003; Egeberg 2003).

Contemporaneous with this rapidly growing number of EUAs (35 in 2013) and their variety in scope, tasks, and powers, scholarly interest in these EUAs has continually increased. In the past few years and especially since the start of the millennium, many articles, books and special issues have been published on the topic of EUAs. Not only is the functioning of these new institutions of interest, but many authors have focused especially on the legitimacy and accountability of these EUAs. This was usually done with a principal-agent approach, applying similar criteria as those often used for the national/state level when assessing the legitimacy of national regulatory agencies or central banks.

2.1. *The legitimacy of EUAs*

The delegation of tasks and powers to non-majoritarian institutions, such as agencies, is often disputed because the democratic legitimacy of such institutions is contested. This is especially the case at the European level because there is no single chain of delegation from the voters through a representative institution (e.g. the European Parliament) to EUAs. This is because the logic of delegation is quite different in the EU system, as it is not the European Parliament (EP) per se that is the principal; rather, it always operates together with its legislative partner, the Council (which is indirectly elected in the national arena).

Moreover, it was possible, until the Lisbon Treaty, for the Council to act on its own in establishing agencies without formally involving the EP. What makes it even more complicated is the fact that the Commission, as a non-legislative actor, can also delegate its powers and tasks to agencies (with the varying involvement of one of the two previously mentioned legislatures) (see Curtin 2009). This implies that, at the European level, there is no single chain of delegation from voters through the European Parliament to agencies. Even in the best case, the EP can be considered only a co-principal (Geradin 2005). As a result, multiple chains of delegation with multiple links at the European level have to be considered. The chain of delegation fragments even further when we look at the delegation of powers at the horizontal EU level, because de facto there are two institutions (the Council and the Commission) performing executive tasks, and both of them delegate powers to a variety of agencies (Curtin 2005, 2007). This setup makes it even more complicated to cope with the well-known ‘principal’s problem’ of how to keep agents under control after delegation (for a detailed discussion, see, for example, Kassim and Menon 2003).

Because this clear chain of delegation is missing at the EU level, it is often disputed that a clear chain of accountability (running in the opposite direction) is detectable for EUAs (Geradin and Petit 2004). But how does this missing or blurred chain of accountability for EUAs affect their legitimacy, and how are they kept under control? Most commonly, it is argued that the agencies’ “output”³ is their (main) source of legitimacy (e.g. Borrás et al. 2007, 586). In Majone’s (2002) opinion, regulatory and efficiency-enhancing policies (in contrast to redistributive policies) do not require a strong normative foundation or strong (political) accountability mechanisms. Hence, EUAs, which he views as problem-solving and efficiency-enhancing entities, do not face the same requirements regarding democratic legitimacy as ‘traditional’ legislative bodies; “the substantive legitimacy provided by accountability-by-results is generally sufficient” (Majone 2002, 18).

However, the mere focus on the output model of legitimacy has been criticized because it ignores the political importance of agencies’ actions and fails to offer a comprehensive response to many important legitimacy concerns, such as distributive effects (see, for example, Shapiro 1997; Skogstad 2003). Thatcher and Stone Sweet (2002) argue that the output model assumes ideological consensus on the role, function, and benefits accrued

³ Scharpf defines output democratic legitimacy as collectively binding decisions that “serve the common interests of the constituency” (Scharpf 1999, 11).

from delegation, whereas these points are often contested by political actors and public opinion. Because of these and other objections to the output model, some authors propose a complementary model of legitimacy for EUAs: procedural legitimacy (see Maggetti 2009, 142f.; Thatcher 2002). This more deliberative model emphasizes the process of decision-making by EUAs and compares them with the insular, often secret deliberation of committees (e.g. comitology) in the EU. If the EUAs' work and decision-making are open and transparent and the agencies are regularly communicating and publishing important information, this may enhance their legitimacy. Thatcher and Stone Sweet (2002, 19) even think that procedural legitimacy can be a fair and democratic substitute for electoral accountability, given the broader purpose of delegation.

Other authors argue that the possible sources of input legitimacy should be kept in mind (see Follesdal 2011; Lindgren and Persson 2010), even though some authors (e.g. Krapohl 2007; Majone 1996) claim that input and output legitimacy are conflicting in regulatory policy. Possible sources for EUAs' input legitimacy could be the participation of the Council and the EP or the participation of civil society (Krapohl 2007, 6). Lindgren and Persson (2010) call this the stakeholder-participation model of input legitimacy. Other authors, in turn (e.g. Geradin and Petit 2004, 52ff.; Vos 2005, 126f.), strongly focus on horizontal accountability relations as sources of legitimacy for EUAs. They claim that EUAs should be especially accountable to the EP (e.g. budgetary power or scrutiny by EP committees) in order to foster legitimacy.

Because of space limitations, only the main arguments concerning EUAs' legitimacy (input, procedural, or throughput and output) and especially the accountability dealt with in the comprehensive literature on EUAs can be presented here. It should be apparent, however, that there is currently vibrant academic discussion of this topic and that no consensus concerning the "right" criteria for assessing EUAs' legitimacy currently exists. Nevertheless, what most of the articles dealing with EUAs' legitimacy have in common is that they mainly focus their analyses and assessments of accountability and legitimacy on the horizontal relations between EUAs and other EU institutions (EP, Council, Commission, Court of Justice) (see, for example, Busuioc 2009; Curtin 2007, 2005; Krapohl 2004; Shapiro 1997; Vos 2005, 2000). Therefore, they tend to neglect one crucial source of accountability and possibly also legitimacy: the vertical relationship between EUAs and the member states

or their national counterparts in the member states. This is even more important because many tasks and responsibilities previously dealt with autonomously by national bodies are now delegated to EUAs or coordinated by EUAs (Eberlein and Newman 2008).

3. EUAs' vertical relationships and accountability

As mentioned above, the existing literature on EUA accountability and legitimacy focuses mainly on the horizontal relationships of EUAs to other EU bodies or institutions.

It is not my intention to argue that such a focus is wrong or misleading; these relationships are certainly very important, and no single process is sufficient to guarantee accountability (see, for example, Olsen 2013). However, in this paper, I put forward the argument that such a limited focus on horizontal relationships overlooks another important set of relationships involving EUAs: the vertical and more direct links to the member states. As compared to the quite indirect link to the member states via relationships to the Council, I argue that the vertical and more direct relationships between EUAs and the particular member states also deserve special attention and in-depth assessment. My main argument for such a focus is that most of the tasks now dealt with by EUAs previously formed part of the portfolio or were the responsibility of NRAs or national actors in general. Therefore, EUAs are now responsible or, in some areas, co-responsible for tasks delegated to them from the member states. In other words, it was not primarily a delegation of tasks from EU institutions (mainly the Commission) to EUAs but actually a delegation of tasks and especially powers from the member state level to EUAs, sometimes with a detour via the Commission. Consequently, I argue that the EU institutions (i.e. the Commission, Council, and EP) are the principals in the sense of being responsible for founding EUAs. However, the member states are also principals, and are no less important, because they have delegated some of their tasks and powers to EUAs (see Curtin 2007). Hence, when applying a principal-agent model, the member states must at least be regarded as co-principals of the EUAs besides the other co-principals, previously mentioned. By acknowledging this chain of delegation from the member states (principals) to the EUAs (agents), one should also expect to find an accountability relationship running in the opposite direction from the EUAs to the particular member states. If such strong links are present, one could speak of an additional channel of input legitimacy for EUAs.

To analyze these vertical relationships, two basic types of vertical interaction/relationships between EUAs and the member states (e.g. the national counterparts) can first be distinguished: (a) formal incorporation of MS representatives in the MBs (steering/management level) and (b) more informal/optional and sometimes even spontaneous/case-by-case inclusion of representatives of national institutions in advisory committees/forums (day-to-day scientific/policy work) and networks (consultation and knowledge exchange).

Thus, on the one hand, a very formal and institutionalized vertical relationship can be observed. All EUAs have a management board (MB) which is responsible for controlling the particular EUA and especially its director. These MBs are made up of at least one representative of each EU member state, allowing the member states to participate and be represented in these EUA bodies. Therefore, this vertical link to the member states is quite obvious and more direct than the often-mentioned linkage via the Council.

On the other hand, there are more informal vertical relationships to the member states (or the national counterparts of the particular EUAs). The best visible instances of such informal links are the so-called advisory forums or scientific committees that are identifiable for many EUAs.

However, although both vertical relationships may be an important source of accountability for EUAs, this paper focuses exclusively on the formal incorporation arrangements. This approach is adopted because only the formal incorporation type may be seen as a source of vertical political accountability⁴, whereas the informal inclusion type is more about peer or professional accountability⁵. Thus, the focus will be on the MBs or, more specifically, on the national representatives on these MBs because they represent the most formal and visible link between the member states and EUAs.

⁴ Political accountability is exercised along the chain of a principal-agent relationship. "Voters delegate their sovereignty to popular representatives, who in turn, at least in parliamentary democracies, delegate the majority of their authorities to a cabinet of ministers. The ministers subsequently delegate many of their authorities to their civil servants or to various, more or less independent, administrative bodies. The mechanism of political accountability operates precisely in the opposite direction to that delegation" (Bovens et al. 2010, 42).

⁵ Peer accountability (a similar concept is called professional accountability [Bovens et al. 2010]) is based on mutual monitoring. Papadopoulos (2010, 2007) defines peer accountability as a situation in which "network participants become primarily accountable to their network partners in soft and horizontal accountability relations" (2010, 1040).

As previously mentioned, EUA MBs have not yet been studied in depth (one exception is the article by Busuioc 2012⁶). Mostly, they are simply treated as organizations which are dominated by member states' appointees and exert control as steering bodies (Zwart and Verhey 2003, 122) over the work of the respective EUAs (MBs' tasks are discussed in more detail in Section 4.1). In the literature on agencies' establishment and design (Kelemen 2002; Kelemen and Tarrant 2011), it is even suggested that the MBs were set up mainly to allow the member states to exert intergovernmental control over agencies after the delegation of tasks and power. Kelemen and Tarrant (2011, 929) argue that this design gives "member states a greater degree of control over EU agencies than they would have enjoyed had the same regulatory tasks been delegated to the Commission".

Because of this design, it is commonly taken for granted that the member states control the EUAs and are able to guide their work and their future development. Accordingly, one could argue that this vertical relationship between the EUA, via its MB, and the member states constitutes a strong political accountability relationship. Thus, by formal design, these vertical relationships could solve the problem of the EUAs' often-criticized lack of political accountability.

However, to serve as a source of political accountability, the national representatives controlling the EUAs should represent the particular national interests in practice and should thus be strongly accountable to the relevant national representative institutions (e.g. government and parliament) and, at the end of the chain of delegation, to the public. To determine whether these formal vertical relationships actually serve as a source of vertical political accountability, it is important to look more closely at the national representatives. In other words, it is important to evaluate the national representatives' particular political accountability to, and dependence on, elected politicians 'at home'.

At one extreme, there are the representatives of national ministries and, at the other, representatives of more or less independent national regulatory agencies (NRAs). As suggested in the literature (see, for example, Egeberg 2003; Egeberg and Trondal 2009; Egeberg et al. 2009.; Follesdal 2011; Trondal 2010), representatives from national ministries possess a clearer chain of delegation and are, therefore, usually more directly accountable

⁶ However, Busuioc mainly focuses on the relationship between EUAs and their directors and the particular MBs respectively.

to, and dependent on, their respective governments (and thus to citizens) than representatives of more or less independent NRAs. Therefore, to assess how the formal inclusion of such representatives affects an EUA's accountability and legitimacy, it is important to find out how accountable and dependent these representatives are vis-à-vis the representative institutions (parliament and government) in their home countries (Eberlein and Newman 2008, 30f.).

At the same time, this paper also offers insights into the attitudes held by EUA MB members on two substantive attitudinal dimensions: perceptions relating to legitimate and accountable EU and EUA governance, and perceptions the preferred level of centralization of political authority in the EU. This evaluation is performed because MB members' attitudes may be expected to have an effect on the behavior of individual MB members or even on EUAs as collective actors (Hooghe 2001, 11, Wonka and Rittberger 2011, 889). This is especially the case in situations of high or unprecedented technical complexity and/or in situations of uncertainty. In contrast, in situations where professional assessments are uncontested or where administrative and political leadership formulates clear mandates and engages in active supervision, MB members' attitudes are expected to exert less influence over the activities of EUA MBs (Wonka and Rittberger 2011).

By investigating not only the accountability of EUA MB members but also their attitudes to EU/EUA governance and levels of centralization, this paper offers a broad picture of EUA MBs and their members.

4. Empirical data

In this part of the paper, empirical data on the accountability and attitudes of EUA MB members are presented. This analysis is based on an original dataset compiled by the author and composed of eight EUAs. The first section justifies the selection of EUAs included in the present analysis. The data on political accountability and political attitudes are then presented, followed by an analysis of domestic political accountability and the attitudes of the MB members.

4.1. *The selection of EUAs*

The empirical insights presented in this paper are based on the study of eight EUAs. The selected EUAs are the European Environment Agency (EEA), the European Medicines Agency

(EMA or EMEA), the Office of Harmonization in the Internal Market (OHIM), the Community Plant Variety Office (CPVO), the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), the European Railway Agency (ERA), the European Agency for the Management of Operational Cooperation at the External Borders (FRONTEX), and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). These EUAs reflect the broad variety of EUA functions, decision-making powers, and tasks. Whereas the EEA, FRONTEX and the ERA mainly have information-gathering and/or coordination tasks, the OHIM, the CPVO, the EASA and the ECHA also possess authoritative decision-making power that is binding on third parties. The EMA, in contrast, has no formal decision-making power but enjoys considerable influence over the adoption of final decisions by the Commission (e.g. Gehring and Krapohl 2007; Geradin and Petit 2004). The selected EUAs cover different policy areas and different phases of agency creation at the European level and are therefore a significant sample of existing EUAs.

What all the selected EUAs have in common is that they all (and every EUA in general) have a management board (MB)⁷ that is responsible for formulating the EUA's strategic objectives and the long-term development plan, for formally adopting the EUA's annual work programme, annual report, budget proposal, and establishment plan, and, usually, for appointing its executive director⁸ (see, for example, Busuioc 2010; Groenleer 2009). Still, there is considerable variance in the composition of these MBs. Usually, every MB is composed of at least one representative (and one alternate) per member state and at least one representative from the Commission. Some EUAs also have representatives from the EP and from stakeholder groups on their board. However, the representatives from the member states always form the majority on these boards⁹ (Busuioc 2010; Geradin 2005; Groenleer 2009; Vos 2005).

4.2. Data collection

The main aim of the research was to collect data about the political accountability and political attitudes of national representatives on EUA MBs. The data presented here were gathered by an online survey conducted in January 2012. This online questionnaire

⁷ Sometimes these MBs are also labeled administrative boards, as is the case for the OHIM (see <http://oami.europa.eu/ows/rw/pages/OHIM/institutional/ABBC/ABBC.en.do>).

⁸ Therefore, the tasks of the MB are separated from the daily decision-making processes in the EUA.

⁹ An exception is the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), whose MB is composed of one representative from the Commission and 14 independent experts appointed by the Council (Groenleer 2009).

contained three sections with questions about accountability, political attitudes, and the work of the MB in general. However, for this paper, only data relating to the representatives' accountability and attitudes are used.

The online survey was conducted among all management board members and their alternates (where they exist) of nine EUAs. Among the 425 management board members surveyed, 127 completed questionnaires were received, which represents an overall response rate of about 30%. However, for this paper, only data for the previously mentioned eight EUAs (i.e. EASA, ECHA, EEA, EMA, ERA, OHIM, CPVO and FRONTEX)¹⁰ and their national representatives are used. This leads to response rates ranging from 22% (EASA) to 44% (ECHA).¹¹ No nationality bias in the data seems to exist. With the exception of Romania, all other countries are represented at least once (Denmark and Spain) in the dataset, the maximum being eight times (Slovenia). The fact that the average de jure political accountability score of the national representatives who filled out the survey is quite similar to the overall score of the respective MBs (for details, see XXX 2011) also indicates that self-selection among respondents did not lead to responses from only a particular type of national representative. Given the moderate response rate and the fact that the survey did not cover all agencies, it is not possible to generalize the results to the overall universe of EUAs. However, it is possible to gain some interesting insights into the accountability and the political attitudes of national representatives on MBs.

4.2.1. Analysis I: Domestic political accountability

Because (de facto) political accountability is not easy to measure, the task was to find indicators and survey questions that could help in approaching this rather wide and complex concept.

One important aspect of the concept of accountability is that an (accountable) actor has the obligation to explain and justify his/her conduct (Bovens 2007, 450). Regular reporting about MB meetings and decision-making may be seen as a way of fulfilling this obligation. The national representatives were therefore asked to specify how often and to whom they are requested to report about their work on the MB.

¹⁰ The EFSA was excluded because there are no national representatives on its MB.

¹¹ The others reached the following response rates: EEA 24%, EMA 30.2%, ERA 30.2%, FRONTEX 30.7%, OHIM 35%, and CPVO 41.3%. Because some representatives did not answer every question, the response rate for some individual items is slightly lower.

As shown in Table 1, most reporting takes place to the line manager and to the respondent's own ministry, department or agency. More than 70% (71.3%) and 71.1% of the MB members indicated that they are requested to report to their line manager or to their own ministry, department or agency *always* or *most of the time*. This indicates a rather strong accountability relationship between most national representatives and their sending institutions.

Table 1 Reporting duties of MB members¹²

Actors	Never	Rarely	About half of the time	Most of the time	Always	N
Own ministry, department, or agency	2 ^a (1.7) ^b	14 (12.3)	17 (14.9)	22 (19.3)	59 (51.8)	114
Line manager	13 (12.0)	10 (9.3)	8 (7.4)	19 (17.6)	58 (53.7)	108
Own government	30 (26.8)	25 (22.3)	17 (15.2)	13 (11.6)	27 (24.1)	112
Own professional community	30 (27.5)	25 (22.9)	21 (19.3)	20 (18.3)	13 (11.9)	109
National public	50 (45.5)	49 (44.5)	5 (4.5)	6 (5.5)	0 (0)	110
Specialized committee of the national	59 (53.2)	41 (36.9)	4 (3.6)	4 (3.6)	3 (2.7)	111
National parliament	66 (59.5)	39 (35.1)	3 (2.7)	3 (2.7)	0 (0)	111
Other EU entities (Council, EP,	72 (67.3)	27 (25.2)	3 (2.8)	2 (1.9)	3 (2.8)	107

^a Absolute numbers; ^b Percentages (modal category in bold)

In contrast, reporting to the government seems to be far less common. Only 35.7% of the national representatives report *always* or *most of the time* to their respective government, whereas 49.1% answered that they *never* or *rarely* do so. However, reporting to a specialized committee of the national parliament or to the parliament in general is even rarer. In both cases, more than 90% (90.1%/94.6% respectively) of the national representatives indicated that they are *never* or *rarely* requested to report to these institutions.

The national representatives were also asked if they are given clear instructions about the positions they should take when acting on the MB, especially when voting (see Table 2). This goes further than expected based on the concept of accountability, because it is not an ex post but rather an ex ante procedure. This indicator is about control (i.e.

¹² Question: How often are you requested to report to the following actors about the EUA management board meetings and decisions made?

independence/dependence) rather than about the accountability of national representatives. Nevertheless, it is an important indicator because, as mentioned in Section 3, MB members’ personal political attitudes, as shown below, may be more or less influential depending on the clarity and reliability of mandates formulated by the administrative or political leadership (see Wonka and Rittberger 2011). This indicator is therefore included in the analysis of representatives’ vertical accountability.

Table 2 Instructions for the national representatives

		I have clear instructions about the “position” I should take:				
		never	rarely	about half of the time	most of the time	always
Total (N: 110)	Number %	16 14.6%	36 32.7%	19 17.3%	26 23.6%	13 11.8%

The data indicate that only 35.4% of the representatives *most of the time* or *always* receive clear instructions about the positions they should take, whereas 47.3% *never* or *rarely* receive such instructions. Accordingly, a majority enjoys quite considerable room for manoeuvre concerning how to vote or, more generally, what position to take when acting on the MBs. This may be seen as an indicator that politicization or, generally, a strong exertion of influence by national governments, as feared by some authors (e.g. Majone 2002), does not take place at the EUA MBs even though they are dominated by national representatives. However, at the same time, this may also strengthen the influence of representatives’ personal attitudes/preferences when deciding and voting on the MB.

The national representatives were also asked how they would describe their role when acting on the MB. The data (see Table 3) show that a majority of the national representatives described themselves as acting in a mixed role (51.4%). However, quite a large proportion (41.3%) indicated that they mainly act as government representatives. Only a very small number (7.3%) described their own role as that of a mainly independent expert.

Table 3 Role perceptions

		How would you describe your role when acting on the EUA Management Board?		
		Mainly as independent expert	Mixed role	Mainly as government representative
Total (N: 109)	Number %	8 7.3%	56 51.4%	45 41.3%

What do these empirical data reveal about MBs' vertical accountability? This is discussed in the conclusion.

4.2.2. Analysis II: Attitudes of national representatives.

In this section, data on the political attitudes or preferences of national representatives on the EUA MBs are presented. On the one hand, the focus is on a conflict dimension that is of crucial importance in EU politics, namely the level of centralization or, more specifically, how competencies and authority should be distributed between the member state and the EU level (i.e. *intergovernmental* vs. *supranational* images of EU governance). On the other hand, I will investigate the attitudes that national representatives hold when it comes to legitimizing the work of EUAs and to holding EUAs accountable (i.e. *democratic* vs. *technocratic* accountability/legitimacy).

In doing so, I can rely on previous studies by Hooghe (2001) regarding the attitudes of Commission staff and Wonka and Rittberger (2011) regarding the attitudes of EUA staff. For the purpose of comparison, I have chosen the same or at least similar indicators to measure the two aforementioned dimensions (see Annex I) and will rely on Hooghe (2001) and Wonka and Rittberger (2011) to choose the indicators measuring the two dimensions. I also run a factor analysis to confirm that the chosen indicators really measure the expected dimensions (see Annex II and Section 4.2.3.). I will now very briefly introduce the two dimensions under study.

4.2.2.1. Level of centralization

The centralization dimension deals with the question of whether national representatives on EUA MBs favor a more centralized or decentralized organization of authority in the EU or, in other words, if they favor a more *supranational* or a more *intergovernmental* allocation of competencies and authority. This means that if the national representatives show more supranational attitudes, this would confirm the so-called "Europeanization thesis" (Eberlein and Grande 2005, 92). The thesis indicates that regulatory functions are increasingly delegated to the EU level to reduce transaction costs and, since EUAs provide independent expertise and information, this delegation enhances the efficiency and the transparency of EU regulatory policy-making (Wonka and Rittberger 2011,

892). Thus, if national representatives share this assessment/thesis, I would expect to observe attitudes favoring supranational centralization.

On the other hand, the “nationalization thesis” (Eberlein and Grande 2005, 93f.) posits that the best solution to regulate domestic markets is not found by giving more competencies to the EU level. Followers of this thesis view the regulatory capacity on the EU level much more critically and may favor more decentralized forms of political regulation. Therefore, national representatives favoring this thesis are expected to show a more intergovernmental attitude (Wonka and Rittberger 2011, 893). One would expect that national representatives with such an attitude would be rather critical of the work of EUAs; they might also be expected to make attempts at least to slow down the delegation of new or more far-reaching tasks to EUAs or even to obstruct the work and development of the respective EUAs (for examples, see Busuioc 2012).

Based on Hooghe (2001) and Wonka and Rittberger (2011), I expect that items 13 to 17 represent national representatives’ attitudes to the level of centralization. Therefore, items 16 and 17 represent the intergovernmental pole, whereas items 13, 14, and 15 represent a supranational attitude.

4.2.2.2. Legitimacy and accountability

For this dimension, I distinguish between two basic principles to legitimize political rule in modern democracies: the *democratic* and the *technocratic* principle (Hooghe 2001; Wonka and Rittberger 2011). The *democratic* principle is based on the chain of representation. In essence, the main focus is on representative institutions (e.g. parliaments) and citizens’ involvement via regular and competitive elections. On the other side, we find the *technocratic* principle. The rapid process of ‘agencification’ in Europe and around the world has fueled a vibrant debate about the role of expertise and a *technocratic* logic to legitimize public policy in general and EU policy-making in particular (see, for example, Majone 2005; Shapiro 1997; Vibert 2007). The *technocratic* principle rests on the assumption that decision-making should be based on the use of value-free and objective criteria, and these kinds of decisions should generate Pareto-optimal solutions (Wonka and Rittberger 2011, 890).

This means that national representatives favoring the *democratic* principle are expected to emphasize strong political accountability relationships, whereas representatives favoring the *technocratic* principle will focus more on professional (Bovens 2007; Bovens et al. 2010) or peer accountability (Papadopoulos 2010, 2007).

Again influenced by Hooghe (2001) and Wonka and Rittberger (2011), I expect items 9 to 12 to reflect this dimension. Therefore, items 9, 10, and 12 should represent the *technocratic* pole, whereas item 11 represents the *democratic* pole.

4.2.3. Results for the attitudinal dimensions.

After presenting the two dimensions of interest (*supranational vs. intergovernmental* and *technocratic vs. democratic accountability/legitimacy*), I now introduce the results of the analysis. First, a factor analysis was run to be sure that the selected items really represent the two dimensions. The factor analysis substantiates that national representatives' preferences/attitudes can be conceptualized along these two proposed dimensions. The results in Annex II include all items with loadings of .6 or higher. The two extracted factors explain 48.2% of the variance. Now let us look more closely at the results.

Technocratic vs. democratic accountability: The first factor (I) captures the dimensions of technocratic vs. democratic accountability. Three of the four expected items load quite high on this dimension. Only item 11 loads rather low and is therefore excluded from further analysis.

These three items are now summarized to obtain one value and to answer the question whether national representatives have technocratic or democratic accountability preferences. Table 4 shows that overall, a mean of 3.9 is reached. This indicates that the national representatives' preferences are quite strongly directed toward a more technocratic perception of accountability. National representatives seem to generally believe in tradeoffs between policy efficiency and democracy. Subjecting EUA decision-making to more democratic control, they seem to fear, would make policy outcomes less efficient. This finding is different from the finding of Hooghe (2001, 74f.) for Commission top officials, as she found a slight tendency toward democratic rather than technocratic attitudes.

Intergovernmentalism vs. supranationalism: This factor (II) captures the traditional conception of European integration as a battle between intergovernmentalism and supranationalism. Again, three items load quite high on this factor. These are the two intergovernmental items 16 and 17, which load positively, and the supranational item 15, which loads negatively. The others load less than 0.6 and are therefore excluded from further analysis. Again, these three items were summarized (first, the negative loading item 15 had to be recoded) to get one overall value for this dimension. The mean (3.4) is a bit lower than for the other dimension. However, it still indicates an intergovernmental tendency of preferences among the national representatives. This result again deviates from the results of Hooghe (2001, 76), as she found a slight supranational tendency for Commission officials.

Table 4 Preferences on the two dimensions

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean ^a	Standard deviation
Technocratic vs. democratic	108	2	5	3.9	.66
Intergovernmental vs. supranational	104	2	5	3.4	.74
Valid values (list wise)	103				

^a Values between 1 (strongly disagree) and 5 (strongly agree)

What these preferences and attitudes of EUA MB members mean for the accountability of EUAs is now discussed in the conclusion.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This paper has addressed the question of the accountability and legitimacy of EUAs and the political attitudes of EUA MB members. The aim was to shed light on a rather unexplored possible source of political accountability: the vertical relationships between EUAs and the member states. The paper also raised the question of whether the EUAs' MBs are genuinely under the national governments' tight control, as often suggested in the literature (see Kelemen and Tarrant 2011) and what attitudes MB members possess.

To assess MB members' vertical accountability relationships and their political preferences/attitudes, new data were collected by an online survey.

To measure their accountability, national representatives were asked about their reporting duties and how often they are requested to report to certain institutions or actors

(domestically and on the EU level). The analysis shows that MB members most often report to their own sending institution or directly to their line manager. Reporting requests by the particular governments, on the other hand, are quite rare, although formally these MB members should act as governmental representatives. Nevertheless, because reporting to the particular sending institutions or line managers is quite common and this is the normal way of account-giving in bureaucracies, there would seem to be a rather strong vertical accountability relationship for EUA MBs.

Additionally, the extent to which national representatives are steered when acting on the MB was also analyzed. The data clearly show that only a minority receives voting or other instructions when acting as a representative on these boards, so they possess considerable room to manoeuvre. The sending institutions and the governments in general seem to refrain from giving direct orders to their representatives. This contradicts claims that the MBs are purely vehicles of governmental control and especially that governments always keep EUAs under control (Kelemen 2002, Kelemen and Tarrant 2011).

The indicated role perceptions of the national representatives fit well with the results presented so far. A slight majority of national representatives described their role as mixed, so they see themselves neither as pure independent experts nor as pure government representatives. On the other hand, slightly more than 40% described themselves as government representatives. This number is, interestingly, quite low, especially if it is borne in mind that these representatives are appointed by their governments and should formally act as government representatives.

Concerning the political attitudes of national representatives, it was demonstrated by a factor analysis that, as expected, two dimensions can be distinguished: *technocratic vs. democratic accountability* and *intergovernmental vs. supranational*. The aggregated scores of the particular items loading on these two dimensions allowed a nuanced analysis of national representatives' political preferences to be carried out. It becomes obvious that national representatives in general show quite strong *technocratic* accountability preferences. A mean of 3.9 (possible values between 1 and 5) clearly shows that this is the case. This is perhaps not surprising since most of these representatives also work at the national level in highly technical and expertise-based policy fields and institutions (e.g.

Egeberg and Trondal 2009, 675). However, a value of 3.9 is still remarkably high in comparison to the study by Hooghe (2001) on Commission officials.

Concerning the preferred level of centralization in the EU (intergovernmental vs. supranational), the direction of political preferences is a little less clear. However, the mean of 3.4 still indicates a slight intergovernmental orientation of most national representatives. The intergovernmental orientation is, remarkably, stronger than that found for Commission officials (Hooghe 2001, 76). This might be explained by the fact that the national representatives are still embedded mainly in the national context in comparison to the Commission officials, who work for a supranational institution (see, for example, Dehousse and Thompson 2012, 120). As mentioned in Section 3, individual preferences are expected to influence individual behavior, especially in situations of uncertainty or when no clear mandates or instructions are present. Because national representatives rarely receive clear instructions about the positions they should take (see Table 2), it may be assumed that they are often guided by their own preferences. Rather technocratic decision-making and reporting behavior (i.e. reporting to their own institution/line manager instead of direct reporting to the government) by the national representatives can therefore be expected. The national representatives' rather intergovernmental attitudes might also explain the opposition to the further delegation of competencies to existing EUAs and other sometimes even destructive behavior of some representatives as reported in some studies (see, for example, Busuioac 2012, 10ff).

Three main conclusions can be drawn from the presented data. Treating these national representatives as pure government representatives falls short of what is required. First, as expected by Egeberg and Trondal (2011, 871), I showed that these national representatives are much more independent and less accountable to their particular governments than expected by EUAs' de jure design (e.g. Kelemen and Tarrant 2011, 929f.). Under these circumstances, it is also questionable whether the MBs are really vehicles by which the member states attempt to exert intergovernmental control over agencies, as is often suggested in the literature (Kelemen 2002; Kelemen and Tarant 2011). Second, the attitudinal data demonstrated that these national representatives possess clear preferences for technocratic accountability of the EU and EUAs in particular. At the same time, weak preferences for a rather decentralized EU (intergovernmental preferences) became obvious.

However, for the purposes of this paper, it is mainly the rather technocratic view of accountability that is of interest because it might also explain the accountability / reporting behavior of the national representatives (i.e. the rather seldom reporting to the government and parliament but regular reporting to their own institution/line manager). Finally, it was argued in this paper that these vertical relationships may be looked at as a source of vertical political accountability for EUAs. However, the data on the formal vertical relationships show a rather ambivalent picture. The political accountability to national representative institutions (i.e. government and parliament) in general is very weak. However, a quite strong indirect accountability relationship via the line manager and the sending institution (be it a ministry or agency) is detectable. That this channel of accountability is more active might be explained, on the one hand, by the normal reporting standards in bureaucracies but possibly also by the strong preference for technocratic accountability shown by EUA MB members. Taken together, this implies that vertical accountability relationships for MBs are detectable, but they qualify as professional rather than as direct political accountability relationships, which may hamper their potential to represent a proper channel of input legitimacy.

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Annex I Table Indicators^{13/14}

1. Although parliaments play an important role in a democracy, they often stand in the way of efficient policy solutions.
2. Great ideological principles never provide solutions to the problems of European citizens.
3. I don't mind politicians and their methods as long as they guarantee reasonably satisfactory public policies.
4. Management board members should be willing to express their ideological conviction, even if they risk conflict with their colleagues.
5. EUAs should not be concerned with public approval of their work.
6. Citizens' influence on political decisions should be improved.
7. The best advice on a proposed policy usually comes from the interests directly affected.
8. EUAs should be independent of industrial interests.
9. The EUA should be held accountable for its work strictly on the basis of professional standards of its area of expertise.
10. In contemporary policy-making, it is essential that expertise be given more weight than political considerations.
11. The MB should have more direct control over the EUA.
12. The basis for EUAs' decisions should be professional judgments and not political interests.
13. The egoistic behavior of some member states threatens the survival of the European project.
14. Too many members of the management board let their nationality interfere with their professional judgment.
15. It is imperative that the European Commission become the true government of the European Union.
16. The member states, not the Commission or the European Parliament, ought to remain the central pillars of the European Union.
17. The strength of Europe does not lie in more power for Brussels but in effective government at the lowest possible level.

¹³ The national representatives could choose for every item whether they *strongly agree, agree, neither/nor, disagree, or strongly disagree*. Hooghe originally used only a four-point scale for her answers (*disagree with reservations, disagree without reservations, agree without reservations, agree with reservations*). She subsequently coded those not answering as "undecided" and introduced this middle category (Hooghe 2001: 69). In my discussion, I treat Hooghe's scale as equivalent to mine.

¹⁴ This list of indicators contains more items than used for this analysis of the mentioned two dimensions because, for other purposes, additional indicators were inquired. However, for reasons of transparency, the whole list of indicators is presented in the annex.

Annex II Table Factor Analysis¹⁵

	Factor	
	I ^a	II ^b
The basis for EUAs' decisions should be professional judgments and not political interests.	.707	
In contemporary policy-making, it is essential that expertise be given more weight than political considerations.	.705	
The EUA should be held accountable for its work strictly on the basis of professional standards of its area of expertise.	.681	
The egoistic behavior of some member states threatens the survival of the European project.		
The MB should have more direct control over the EUA.		
Too many members of the management board let their nationality interfere with their professional judgments.		
The member states, not the Commission or the European Parliament, ought to remain the central pillars of the European Union.		.850
The strength of Europe does not lie in more power for Brussels but in effective government at the lowest possible level.		.804
It is imperative that the European Commission become the true government of the European Union.		-.668
Eigenvalue	2.38	1.96

Extraction method: Principal components

Rotation method: Varimax

KMO: 0.663

^a Technocratic vs. Democratic accountability/legitimacy

^b Intergovernmentalism vs. Supranationalism

¹⁵ In this table, only the factor analysis for the items expected to represent the two dimensions is shown. However, if the factor analysis is run with all indicators listed in Annex I, the same two factors plus two additional ones can be extracted.